

Development value of childhood disease

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In many biographies and autobiographies one finds descriptions of great developmental spurt in children as a consequence of *severe* disease. I have seen this a few times here among our handicapped children and remember in particular two mongol children who, going through a severe attack of measles, one with pneumonia, making not only great headway in their development, but also nearly shedding their mongoloid features.

Now that does not mean that we should cultivate illness or try to create conditions for infectious diseases to bring about such spurts of development. It rather means that a person grows and matures by facing and conquering frustrations rather than by getting along unhindered and unimpeded.

Human destiny and personality develop as a response to challenge, as do the destinies of groups of people as well as human cultures. Illness, therefore, can be seen as part of the meaningful unfolding of a person's life and destiny and not only as an affliction that should be prevented or, at least, nipped in the bud.

However, therapy too is a valid aspect. I actually decided to study medicine after I had read a book by Paul de Cruif *Fighters against Death and Devil*. That is what medicine tries to be today: An aggressive reaction to what we think are aggressive entities. We "fight" infection, we "exterminate" bacteria, we "kill" pain (an interesting concept really, that one can "kill" pain). While this may be a valid and successful approach it is not the only one. It is today so exclusively in the foreground because we have not yet matched the intellectual advancement we have made in the natural scientific field with our intuitive, imaginative, artistic and particularly moral interpretation of human phenomena.

I would like to sketch a few pictures, and it is really no more than that—to show one possible approach to the aspect of the meaning of illness as an event in the course of development, in the course of the unfolding of destiny.

Now when we think of the infectious children's diseases one can possibly select four as representative, as being particularly impressive in their images. Scarlet Fever, Whooping Cough, Measles and Diphtheria. When one has encountered a child in such an illness, one can look at the illness as one would regard a painting or a sculpture, a landscape or also the face of another person, rather than with a scientific scrutiny; not asking what causes these symptoms and what can be done about them, but purely allowing oneself to be impressed by what confronts one and to allow oneself to have a completely subjective reaction to what one sees. One can observe in a child who falls ill with scarlet fever, with the dark-red, hot dry face and the white ring around the mouth, the dramatic beginning of the illness. There is no long incubation or prodrome. The illness usually starts suddenly. I remember my scarlet fever started on Christmas Eve. Our family was waiting for Christmas to begin. We always had a big celebration at Christmas with a Christmas tree. The whole family assembled in one room in the evening, until the doors were opened and we saw the lit Christmas tree. I shivered; my throat burned. I went cold and hot at the same time. I vomited and was taken away into my parents' bedroom. My mother must have known what the matter was straight away. I was isolated for seven or eight weeks and only my mother entered my room. I missed the whole of Christmas, it was really terrible; then one of my presents was brought to me which had to be burned afterwards.

I had two other siblings. Neither of them got scarlet fever but I still remember the turmoil that my illness caused in my family and my feeling of complete re-birth when I recovered. When later, as a young physician, I saw children going through scarlet fever, I was impressed by the flame and fiery nature of this illness and its power of catharsis.

I remember seeing children in the parks who had whooping cough. What a dreadful struggle and how completely different a picture! One would hardly think that if scarlet fever were an illness this could be an illness as well. One met a different world, a completely different mode of existence. These children were wrestling for breath. Breathing which is normally a rhythmic, easy, harmonious process had suddenly become cramped, frozen; you could practically see how the heads of these children had jumped down into their chests and into their lungs, and there formed a hard, frozen balloon that they had to try to eject with tremendous effort, pain and force. Just as in scarlet fever one could see the heat and fire of metabolism flooding the organism, so I thought, in pertussis, the air that should yield to rhythm and flow was becoming independent, clenching and gripping the breath in a vice.

I have never had measles myself, but I have often seen it. Particularly when it is not too severe, I always thought it looked a bit ridiculous. It called up in me the memory of the burbling, gurgling noise of air being submerged in water. When I came over to this country I found that measles is not such a ridiculous thing here. It can be quite a serious illness and has, in fact, somewhat the place that scarlet fever had on the continent. I wondered whether there was perhaps more reality in the drowning phenomenon if one is an islander while I had come from a very land-locked part of Europe, where water did not mean the sea, but rather rain or small rivers and beautiful lakes.

I had, quite early, nearly as my first childhood memory, at the age of five

years, an encounter with diphtheria. My sister, who is five years younger than I, fell dramatically ill with diphtheria, when she was quite a young infant. We were having breakfast at a round table. I can still see the pink tablecloth and my mother holding my sister in her arms as she was still a baby. I was very fond of my sister and suddenly she seemed to go away. I thought she was dead. She had gone quite white, began to choke and then it looked as if somebody were strangulating her. Having gone white, she then went blue and cold; that was all I saw. An ambulance arrived and took my sister and my mother away to hospital. After a tracheotomy, my sister survived in an isolation glass cubicle, retaining only a deep shock memory of people in white coats.

Perhaps one can see the four elements in these four images of childhood diseases; the fire in scarlet fever, the air in pertussis, the water in measles, the earth in diphtheria.

Now it is interesting that while all these diseases can befall an adult, they are nevertheless regarded as childhood diseases. Perhaps they are also distinguishable from other illnesses by their particular, nearly rhythmic, mode of progress. They have a beginning and an end and usually take a definite time, perhaps most clearly with the 28 days of measles, where after 11 days of incubation you get the short prodromal state, then the flaring-up of the rash, and finally resolution and recovery. Other illnesses do not seem to have a time structure to the same extent, though some such features can perhaps be distinguished.

But the question remains why these illnesses are more typical for children than for adults. Of course, we can say adults have become immune by infection in childhood; that is certainly one aspect of the question. But there is perhaps another aspect. Infection is altogether an interesting phenomenon; you can get an infection without an infecting agent like a bacterium or virus. You can get infectious laughter, you can get infectious chorea; we have had epidemics of hysteria not caused by microscopic organisms but by affection and imitation. These, of course, are essential elements in the nature of childhood, in fact, only with their help can a child develop and learn. The isolation of a child who has measles or scarlet fever from other children does perhaps not only restrict the micro-organisms but rather the other aspects of affection and imitation. A certain taboo is placed on the illness and that, if it is strongly maintained, can be quite effective. It is even possible that some of our remedies work in a similar way.

My argument so far has really just been that childhood diseases have something to do with childhood and I would, therefore, now like to look at child development in the same imaginative, subjective way. Now we usually say that children "grow up". This seems reasonable, but is due to the fact that we look from the vantage point of the adult at the child who is "not yet grown-up". But what do we really see when we look at the growing child with an impressionable, unprejudiced mind?

Sixty days after conception, the human embryo's head has about the same weight and volume as the rest of the body. Before birth, the foetus in the womb takes up a position that resembles the form of the brain. The head is the frontal pole, the back the parietal, the bottom of the foetus the occipital pole, the feet the cerebellum, the umbilical cord the spinal cord, the arm the lateral fissure, the knee the temporal lobe. An outline tracing of the foetus in the womb appears identical to an outline tracing of the adult brain. Throughout the development from the embryo to the adult, distal and caudal growth always exceeds proximal and cranial growth. The face, and particularly the lower jaw,

grow more than the forehead, the legs more than the arms, the trunk more than the head. Growth is always and consistently downwards.

The new-born child has no voluntary motor control; he cannot stand, cannot sit. He has to be held in his mother's arm, or lies in his cot. While the new-born calf or foal is dropped to the ground and immediately begins to wriggle on to its long, sturdy legs and, still swaying to and fro, lifts its small head to the mother's teat to drink, the human infant takes a whole year to descend slowly from head to toes down into its body. In the first month the child gains control of the eye movements. By the second month he can lift his head, by the third his shoulders. Then by the fourth and fifth months he is able to bring his hands together and grasp objects he has seen. By the age of six months, the child can sit up, by nine months kneel and crawl, by ten months stand and by the end of the first year, walk. Motor control has descended step by step, month by month, downward from head to feet. The child has grown down and now reaches to the earth.

This visible downward growth is, however, only the last phase of a much greater progress of descent, to some extent depicted in the ancient mysteries, but newly described by Rudolf Steiner at the beginning of the century. It is the descent of the human individuality and form from the great expanse of the cosmos that precedes each conception. The Kabbala describes archetypal Man, Adam Kadmon, as expanded throughout the Zodiac. His brow in Aries, throat in Bull, shoulders in Twin, chest in Cancer, heart in Lion, belly in Virgin, hips in Libra, sex organs in Scorpio, thighs and upper arms in Archer, knee and elbow in Sagitarius, calf and lower arm in Waterman, hand and foot in Fishes. Plato in his dialogues "Symposium" and "Timaios", make reference to this expanded, spherical man. Our own time regards the Zodiac either as superstition, as of no account, or more recently among the young and not so young as a kind of fetish to hang around one's neck or as a reliable omen according to one's birthdate. We do not seem to realize that the Zodiac is the most accurate means of ascertaining the relative positions of sun and earth, the source of all life, of all existence. The Zodiac is the scale and measure of the source of energy and life, the special relation between sun and earth. It is as little a fetish or superstition as a ruler or slide scale would be.

The triad of squares that forms the twelvefold Zodiac is the origin of man's threefold as well as of his fourfold nature. The threefoldness of head and sense system, circulatory system and limb system as well as of thought, feeling and will, and equally the fourfoldness of form, life, sensitivity and awareness of self, or physical, etheric, astral and ego, as Steiner put it.

The four great childhood diseases can be seen as the individuality wrestling with the individual establishing of his fourfold organization. In diphtheria, the physical body wrestles with earth; in measles the ether body tries to individualize the waters of life; in whooping cough the sentient nature tries to overcome the air, and in scarlet fever the ego seeks to establish itself. Perhaps these images can be taken as a starting point for our discussions.